

PECULIARITIES OF INVESTIGATING PROVERBS AND SAYINGS
IN LINGUOCULTURAL ASPECT

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Abstract: *The article emphasizes the importance of proverbs and sayings as cultural artifacts. They reveal historical events, everyday life, and the worldview of a people, enriching language with wit and insightful observations.*

Keywords: *proverbs linguoculture, cultural values, folkloric origin, didactic content, worldview*

The study of proverbs and sayings from a cultural perspective has highlighted the need to identify and compare different types of culture reflected in language. In addition to linguoculturological (ethnocultural) analysis of language, sociocultural analysis of language and speech is also necessary. The culturological study of language involves the study of the genre and stylistic features of texts in which the cultural priorities of civilization, ethnicity, and social order are expressed in the most concise form. Such texts include proverbs and sayings - works of folk oral art, which have not yet been specially studied in the cultural and linguistic aspect.

Proverbs are like nuggets of wisdom passed down through generations. They capture typical situations in life and offer guidance or express emotions in a condensed way. Some scholars, like C.C. Doyle, see them as mini folk poems that add flavor to conversations or writing. Both folklore and linguistics study proverbs [2:4].

One key reason for studying proverbs, as highlighted by Taylor, Seiler, Firth, Mieder, and others, is their traditional nature. They are often seen as anonymous, passed down from unknown sources, and not part of formal literature. While this is somewhat true, proverbs can also have specific authors or origins. Despite this, they are studied as part of folklore and distinguished from similar expressions like

idioms, clichés, and slogans. Linguistics also analyzes proverbs as sentences, conversational elements, and acts of speech, differentiating them from idioms and phrases.

Proverbs are simple and concise sayings, known and repeated among the people, expressing a truth based on common sense or practical experience of mankind. These are traditional sayings that give advice or expound morality in a short and meaningful form.

Proverbs are found in all world languages and cultures, and they are often borrowed from other languages and cultures. The origin of proverbs is often unknown and it is not easy to trace their origin. Proverbs are often found among both literate and illiterate people and are transmitted orally. Proverbs go deep into human history, and they are not limited to a specific country, culture, or language. Moreover, although proverbs are often borrowed from similar languages and cultures, sometimes they reach the present day through more than one language and culture.

"A saying is a widely used figurative expression that accurately defines a certain life phenomenon. Unlike proverbs, to which they are close in form, sayings are devoid of direct instructive meaning and are limited to a figurative, often allegorical definition of a phenomenon." [5:57].

The main characteristic of a proverb is its completeness and didactic content. A proverb differs by the incompleteness of inference, the absence of didactic character.

Proverbs and sayings are essential material for studying historical events, ethnography, everyday life, and the worldview of the people. Having stood the test of time, they have seamlessly merged with speech; they will always adorn it with wit, the ability to succinctly and accurately characterize the diverse manifestations of life.

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